

Teaching as part of open scholarship – Scientometric indicators for open educational resources*

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Abstract

Scientometric indicators for recording Open Educational Resources (OER) could provide a way of quantitatively representing openness in higher education teaching. They could serve science policy monitoring and lead to greater visibility of higher education teaching in the recognition and reward system which is currently not the case. In order to explore opportunities and risks as well as potential effects of such OER indicators, focus group discussions with experts from the OER and/or scientometric community were conducted in summer 2022. This paper presents the results. In the group discussions, the complexity of OER materials became clear and participants also highlighted that their representation through scientometric indicators has to take into account specificities. The participants rated usage of OER indicators on an individual level, e. g. in the context of appointment procedures for academic staff, as highly problematic and not desirable. Scientometric indicators in general represent a reduction of complexity in this respect and do not reflect quality adequately. Institutional applications and applications to identify a cultural change towards open teaching practices, on the other hand, are rated rather positively. By such applications, the implementation of OER policies could be monitored and universities could develop a teaching profile based on openness.

Introduction

Teaching is an essential part of the science system, yet it often does not appear in science evaluations or rankings of science institutions (e.g., the evaluation of the excellence strategy in Germany; Möller, Schmidt & Hornbostel, 2015). We think this is contradictory and an imbalance emerges regarding an academic community's claim to provide good teaching and to support the next generation on the one hand, and the lack of appreciation of good teaching on the other hand. Thus, teachers who invest a lot of time and effort in their lectures tend to be punished by being evaluated poorly as they have less time to conduct research and to publish the results. We therefore explore potential performance indicators that measure teaching performance.

In addition to investigating the lack of appreciation of teaching, which goes hand in hand with the lack of consideration in performance evaluations, we also address the implementation of open scholarship strategies with the potential performance indicators for university teaching. As open scholarship encompasses the disclosure of all scholarly practices, processes and products, it also explicitly includes the open design of teaching (Mayrberger & Thiemann, 2018; Tennant et al., 2019).

Teaching practices seem to be largely cut off from other efforts in science to make activities and results open and to value these efforts also by means of performance indicators. This happens although openness is both demanded by the scientific communities and highly encouraged and supported by policy-makers (European Commission, 2019).

The measurement of open teaching/learning materials is particularly conceivable in the context of the growing community surrounding Open Educational Resources (OER). OER represent open learning/teaching resources and research materials that can be shared, edited, processed and redistributed depending on the degree of openness (UNESCO, 2019). OER provide unrestricted access to learning resources. For teachers, OER can also be seen as an opportunity

*Note: Authorship is evenly split at 50/50%. The order of authorship is alphabetical and has no further meaning

to gain recognition for their efforts in teaching, as their activities in this regard become visible through open practices and OER. Moreover, openly licenced learning and teaching materials offer opportunities for exchange among teachers and the corresponding discussion of open questions (D'Antoni, 2009).

From a scientometric point of view, OER offer the possibility to analyse freely accessible teaching material and thus to expand academic performance evaluation to include teaching activities. This approach is reflected in the German Research Foundation (DFG) demand. In May 2022, the DFG published a position paper calling for research funders to broaden the range of accepted publication formats and to use scientometric indicators in a less restricted way (DFG, 2022, 5). The DFG's statements relate purely to scientific research output, in particular publications, but not to learning and teaching materials from the field of higher education teaching. Teaching is an essential part of science. Therefore, we discuss the development of an indicator set for learning and teaching materials, especially OER as they are openly available. In order to analyse the suitability of OER indicators for making higher education teaching more visible, the basic attitude to scientometric indicators for OER as well as potential effects and impacts, we asked members of the scientific community to discuss the idea of OER indicators. The research questions are:

- (1) How do experts in OER and/or scientometrics assess scientometric indicators for OER as a tool to make higher education teaching efforts more visible?
- (2) What potential effects and impacts could OER indicators imply?

Methodologically, we used focus group discussions for this purpose. This paper discusses the findings from these focus groups.

Theoretical background

Open scholarship and open educational resources (OER)

Openness in the academic world is an evolving trend that builds on the support of the scientific community as well as on demands made by policy-makers and providers of funding. Open scholarship refers to all efforts that serve to make scientific activities, processes and the resulting products freely accessible. Besides research activities, open scholarship includes practices and circumstances happening before research as such takes place (e.g. mentoring, collaborations, pre-registrations, etc.) and after the act of research (all kinds of data and knowledge exchange). The term also includes scientific activities that are not research practices itself (like data analysis and interpretation) but are directly related to them, such as teaching (Veletsianos & Kimmons, 2012).

Besides the term open scholarship, concepts on open science and open educational practices coin discussions on openness in research and higher education teaching. Mayrberger and Thiemann (2018) show the relationship between different concepts (Table 1).

**Table 1. Open Science/Scholarship, Open Research & Open Education.
(Mayrberger & Thiemann, 2018, 89)**

<i>Open Science and Scholarship</i>		
<i>Open Research</i>		<i>Open Education</i>
Open Research Practices	Practices	Open Educational Practices
Open Access	Products	OER
Open Data	Evidence	Open Data as OER

They distinct between practices, products and evidence - both for open research and for open education. The latter is relevant for the present work. Definitions of the practices and products of open education are often not distinct, nor are they always clear. Bellinger and Mayrberger (2019) point out in their literature review that academic papers draw on a highly varied understanding of open educational practices (OEP). Roughly speaking, the different understandings of OEP can be divided into two perspectives, both attached to the products OER. On the one hand, there is the belief that OEP cannot be implemented without OER. In these cases, reference is usually made to David Wiley's 5 Rs (2014), which state that in the best (or most open) case, educational materials can be retained, revised, remixed, reused and redistributed. On the other hand, the use of OER as described by the 5Rs are not seen as absolutely necessary in open educational contexts (Hegarty, 2015). In other words, in this case openness in education is based on a very broad definition of OER, where availability plays the major role, not openness in a sense of revising and remixing learning materials without copyright restrictions.

It is important to acknowledge that from a definition point of view, it is not always clear whether an educational resource is an OER or not. Kerres and Heinen distinguish between weak and strong OER. Weak OER are all digital educational resources that are openly accessible (reuse and retain) without a paywall. Strong OER allow revising, remixing and redistributing (Kerres & Heinen, 2015, 26).

What seems clear is that openness in the teaching context plays a role in different areas. From an educational policy perspective (regarding the design of high-quality university teaching), from a socio-political perspective (to reduce the cost of educational materials), but also from a pragmatic perspective, open educational contexts play a role in lowering the threshold to access to educational materials and making them easily accessible (Bellinger & Mayrberger, 2019, 20-21).

It seems equally uncontroversial that the implementation of OER vision meets some obstacles. The Capetown Open Education Declaration (2007) identifies four of these barriers at the societal level: “Most educators remain unaware of the growing pool of open educational resources. Many governments and educational institutions are either unaware or unconvinced of the benefits of open education. Differences among licensing schemes for open resources create confusion and incompatibility. And, of course, the majority of people in the world does not yet have access to the computers and networks that are integral to most current open education efforts.” Five obstacles can be identified regarding personal obstacles and barriers that might prevent teachers from designing and using OER: (1) Lack of time (2) Legal uncertainty (3) Technical hurdles (4) Finding material (5) Lack of acceptance (Otto, 2020). In order to overcome the personal difficulties and to let the advantages come to bear, it can be helpful to create science-political incentive structures, alongside a promotion of OER and ensurance that teachers who invest effort and work in the creation of teaching materials are duly appreciated.

Measurement of openness

Open scholarship indicators can be based on scientometric measurement methods. They record openly accessible products and practices and can provide insights into how openly a person, institution or country is working. The Open Science Monitor¹, for example, tracks the

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/open-science-monitor_en

development of open practices in Europe by monitoring open access publications, open research data and open collaboration on the level of EU countries and individual disciplines. In this case, scientometric recording is used for monitoring. Scientometric indicators are known to have a steering effect. Products and practices that are recorded scientometrically in academic performance measurements for example are made visible and possibly also rewarded. Consequently, there are positive effects for academics if they orient their academic practices to an existing recognition and reward system (Hicks et al., 2015). In this case, the indicators also function as an incentive structure (Pampel et al., 2020).

Open Scholarship indicators focus predominantly on research practices and products (including open data, open code, open peer review, etc.). It should be noted that a discussion has started about the shortcomings of current reward and recognition systems in science and a change towards a broader view of performance can be observed (DORA, 2019; VSNU et al., 2019).

In this context, at the evaluation level of academics, reference should be also made to ACUMEN and OS-CAM. By including teaching indicators, both approaches are fundamental to making teaching activities visible and appreciating them, they act as incentives. The portfolio “Academic careers understood through measurement and norms” (ACUMEN²) gives academics the opportunity to present their own academic achievements as multi-layered and inclusive as possible. For example, the *creation of textbooks, online courses, teaching awards* and the *number of views of teaching presentations* can be indicated there and thus made visible. The “Open Science Career Assessment Matrix” (OS-CAM; see: European Commission, 2017) also presents a performance assessment that takes openness factors into account. With regard to university teaching, information can be presented there subject to the keywords *teaching, mentoring* and *supervision*. Unlike the Open Science Monitor, ACUMEN and OS-CAM both operate at the level of individual academics but are in contrary to the Open Science Monitor not based on quantity.

Those examples show that tools to make openness and teaching activities visible, already exist and can be applied. In our paper, we address the question of whether a concept for OER indicators could bridge the gap between the two areas. To explore the impact of such a concept, potential OER indicators were drafted and presented to focus group participants for discussion.

Method

We organized three focus group discussions between May and July 2022. Each focus group included between three and six participants. There were 13 participants in total. The conversations lasted a maximum of two hours each. The focus group method lends itself to our study because it ensures that different perspectives are heard and mutually enrich each other through interaction among the participants: "The hallmark of focus groups is the explicit use of the group interaction to produce data and insights that would be less accessible without the interaction found in a group" (Morgan, 1990, 12). Focus groups provide insight into the range of opinions of the entire group, as the exchange of arguments is analysed and evaluated at the end. The study is not about capturing individual opinions (Merton, Fiske & Kendall, 1956).

Our focus groups consisted of researchers with expertise in either scientometric measurements and/or open scholarship and OER. Experts were contacted directly by email and asked to participate. We ensured an even distribution in gender and research experience, included female and male participants, and PhD students, post-docs and professors. All participants work in Germany. The focus group discussions took place online.

² <http://research-acumen.eu/>

Our preparation for the focus groups consisted of a presentation of outlined OER indicators, as subject of discussion. The indicators were introduced at the beginning of each focus group (see appendix 1). In theory, existing open scholarship indicators could be transferred to the subject of OER. Where classical open scholarship products like e. g. open access publications or open research data are counted, OER could be counted in the area of teaching material. Where the degree of openness of open access publications is recorded using the green, hybrid or golden road labels, the licences of teaching materials could serve to determine how open the materials are. Traditional bibliometric and altmetric indicators can also be applied to both open research material and OER. It would thus be possible to record how often an OER was cited, how often it was downloaded, viewed or shared on social media channels.

Table 2. Transfer of existing Open Access Indicators to OER. (for the Open Access Indicators see: Danish Open Access Indicator³ & Altmetrics Manifesto⁴)

<i>Open Access Indicators</i>	<i>OER Indicators</i>
number	OER count
openness	degree of openness (weak, strong OER) granularity of OER (low, medium, high)
citations	citations of OER
downloads	downloads of OER
views	views of OER
bookmarks	bookmarks of OER
social media count	social media conversations about OER
re-use	reuse of OER

In fact, there are several obstacles to consider because OER which are designed exclusively for teaching/learning purposes differ from scientific publications in many aspects. Some difficulties were briefly touched upon in the presentation and were then taken up and further discussed by the participants. Among these aspects is the diverse granularity of OER which comes along with different types of OER (e. g. videos, slides, exercises) as well as the degree of openness depending on copy rights allocated to a resource by its creator. It must be kept in mind that the discussion was not conducted at the level of individual OER indicators as outlined in table 2, but that the overarching research questions from chapter one were placed at the centre of the discussions. Apart from the brief presentation of the exemplary OER indicators and the research questions, the focus groups were not structured. There was no guideline. Our intervention was limited to answering comprehension questions as well as inquiries if, from our point of view, a clarification of how exactly a contribution was meant, was necessary.

The focus groups were then transcribed by external service providers (all transcripts are available in German and can be found in appendix 2). The transcripts were afterwards analysed in a three-step process according to Bohnsack (2021). The first two steps are carried out in relation to the focus group discussions standing on their own, only in the third step are the focus group discussions brought together. The first step involved “*formulating interpretation*” (in German: “*formulierende Interpretation*”; Bohnsack, 2021, 138) of the individual discussions, which means that issues raised are identified. The first step was carried out independently by the two authors. Inductively, we extracted codes from the text. In the subsequent “*reflective interpretation*” (in German: “*Reflektierende Interpretation*”; Bohnsack. 2021, 139), the codes

³ <https://www.oaindikator.dk/en/>

⁴ <http://altmetrics.org/manifesto/>

within the individual transcripts were set in relation to each other, by considering the terms in their conversational context. Umbrella concepts were found and first codebooks emerged for each transcript. Afterwards, the three codebooks were discussed and condensed into a final codebook (the final coding and codebook as a result of analysis step 2 can be found in appendix 3, the quotes used in this paper to underline our findings are translated to English). In the last step, the “*formation of types*” (in German: “*Typenbildung*”; Bohnsack 2021, 145), the themes identified with their respective references in the individual conversations are analysed on a metalevel in order to highlight overarching patterns. The types are represented in chapter four as headlines of the subchapters.

Remarkably, the research method of focus group discussion reflects subjective assessments. Our work does not claim to represent the impact and effects of the OER indicators in their completeness. In this sense, the advantage of the method is at the same time its limitation.

Results

Assessment of the opportunities and limitations of the OER indicators

Basic attitude towards scientometric indicators

The focus group participants shared a fundamental scepticism and criticism of scientometric methods. In particular, the impact factor and the H-index were used as examples of indicators that were often applied poorly or misleadingly. Overall, qualitative methods were favoured over quantitative assessment approaches (e. g. appendix 2, line 522 – 523, 2158 – 2160). Participants criticised that scientometrics tempts to erroneously conclude from quantity to quality (e.g. appendix 2, line 172 - 177). Furthermore, they criticised that simple indicators often prevail over more complex ones because their application is cheaper and they can be implemented with fewer obstacles (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1319 - 1326, 2155 – 2158, 1331 - 1341). Both arguments against scientometric methods suggest that the indicators are overestimated regarding their informative value and thus interpretations are misleading and unjustified science policy decisions result. This scepticism is also expressed towards the potential OER indicators. They are discussed in the context of the critique of scientometric methods.

Qualitative evaluation procedures that should be preferred according to the participants (especially peer reviews as a central scientific quality assurance instrument) are very complex (e. g. appendix 2, lines 401 - 407). Future performance evaluation based on comprehensive qualitative assessments of teaching material is therefore classified as desirable, but not practical and very unlikely. Participants refer to the practical relevance and good manageability of scientometric indicators (e. g. appendix 2, lines 938 - 941). Furthermore, a steering function is attributed to them in the current system of science evaluation:

... I would like to introduce the indicators first in order to make teaching an equal object in the evaluation (appendix 2, 231 – 232)

... So from that perspective, to say we suggest an indicator to create a taste for teaching as performance, that can work, as I said, that can work. Because now you suddenly have something you can sort by (appendix 2, 943 – 944)

The overall range with regard to OER indicators stretches from firm rejection (e. g. appendix 2, lines 2192 - 2199) to a fundamentally positive attitude (e. g. appendix 2, lines 231 - 237). The following contribution illustrates the two opposing positions very well:

... Oh, not more indicators. That was my first thought [...] I also have the impression that quantity is more important than quality in the scientific field and I would simply be afraid

or worried that this would lead to an intensification. On the other hand, I can also imagine that this, yes, somehow/it is about making the use of OER in teaching visible and about practising openness in university teaching. And what is also an impression on my part is that in any procedures, we have just talked about applications, or Ms. Weimer mentioned the classic appointment procedure for professorships, that this quantity is valued even more, that is, more attention is paid to paper publishing, third-party funding and so on, than to what is actually done in teaching. So much less attention is actually paid to the aspects of teaching. And for this, it could perhaps be a good means of bringing teaching back to the fore in such procedures, if it is somehow framed in the area of openness. I think that would be good (appendix 2, 2167 – 2180)

Measurement targets

All participants agreed on the need for greater visibility of higher education teaching, which is one goal of OER indicators. It seemed to be undisputed that this visibility of higher education teaching is currently only present to a small extent and should be expanded (e. g. appendix 2, lines 638 – 643, 2177 - 2184). The fundamental suitability of OER as a tool for making teaching visible as a measurement goal of an OER indicator was assessed differently. Positive voices saw OER as a suitable medium for this purpose (e. g. appendix 2, lines 726 - 727):

... OER is accessibility, making things visible. [...] That means we shouldn't talk about quality or see that as another dimension, but we should talk about what it means to make visible here. And I believe that the way open access makes science visible, also for a community and others, although I prefer the word accessibility [...] also how I think about OER (appendix 2, lines 687 – 693)

At the same time, however, there were also negative assessments. The relationship between the measured object of OER as open teaching material and the respective teaching actually carried out was rated as unclear (e. g. appendix 2, line 624 - 640). Overall, OER were consistently seen as only a part of teaching and not as representative of teaching as a whole (e. g. appendix 2, lines 84 - 90, 533 - 547, 722 - 724).

... But that means the OER is the resource [...] the material. Not the teaching. (appendix 2, line 845)

... OER is, so to speak, I would say, an add-on to good teaching. But it does not stand for good teaching. Good teaching is characterised by the fact that educational processes are initiated, but not by the fact that OER are created. So I would make a big distinction there. For me, OER would be an add-on (appendix 2, lines 1991 – 1995)

Furthermore, the openness of teaching/learning material OER was seen as problematic. Teachers for whom OER are not a suitable type of material for personal reasons or due to the characteristics of the subject being taught could be disadvantaged in an OER-based indicator system and thus remain invisible.

... And if my subject, which has already been mentioned several times, is a subject in which OER do not play any role and in which I cannot integrate OER in a meaningful way, for whatever reason, or really only very selectively, then it is somehow no longer comparable with a subject where I can run it in a continuous loop, so to speak, both are very, yes, exaggerated. And if I'm a person who simply doesn't like dealing with OER, and I can perhaps use other methods to convey the content much more authentically, then OER won't help me. (appendix 2, lines 512 – 519)

In summary, participants in the focus groups see OER as a part of teaching as a larger whole. From all the contributions to the discussion together, no clear opinion can be derived as to whether OER and an OER indicator are suitable for raising visibility of higher education teaching.

Measurement results

As could be expected, the measurement results of an OER indicator and its significance were also critically assessed against the background of the basic attitudes towards scientometric indicators. In particular, the question of the meaning and significance of OER indicators was raised (e. g. appendix 2, lines 258 - 268, 342 - 349). The first difficulty addressed in this context was the relationship between the measurement carried out and the actual measurement objective.

... the question is what you have measured - what you want to assess and represent somewhere? So do you actually have this reference, does it actually represent it correctly? And that, I think, is always the difficulty, where you have to be clear about what you want to measure and whether it is represented by data, or where there are weaknesses in the data, where there are distortions. I think that is always the very difficult point when it comes to quantitative evaluations (appendix 2, lines 1152 – 1158)

The measurement of individual performance through an OER indicator was consistently viewed critically. Measurements at the level of institutions, on the other hand, were viewed much more positively (see chapter 4.1.5).

The possibility of drawing conclusions about the quality of the teaching practised through measurement results of an OER indicator was rejected (e. g. appendix 2, line 700 - 702), but at the same time an emphasis on the quality aspect was urged (e. g. appendix 2, line 2397 - 2411). In this context, the possibility that the openness of OER could indirectly improve the quality of teaching was also discussed (e. g. appendix 2, lines 705 – 711).

Measurement object

As already mentioned, the fundamental suitability of OER as a measurement object for making higher education teaching visible was considered controversial. Furthermore, the particularities of OER as an object of measurement compared to conventional scientometrically measurable products and documents (e.g. articles or books) were addressed from a more technical perspective.

For instance, participants discussed the different forms (e. g. appendix 2, lines 2278 – 2283) and granularities of OER (e. g. appendix 2, lines 32 - 38), which poses a challenge for scientometrics. OER can have a very fine granularity (for example, short exercises or small-scale figures) or a high granularity (for example, OER as entire online courses). Furthermore, OER were assigned rather static or rather dynamic characteristics due to the inherent dynamism of a subject and the associated rapid adaptation of the subject matter, which is related in particular to the characteristics of the teaching subject (e. g. appendix 2, lines 189 – 192). In addition, OER can be seen as finished "high-gloss materials", equivalent to scientific papers, or as unfinished material that can be further processed by the teaching community (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1895 - 1902).

The topic of versioning OER was also considered to be highly relevant for the implementation of OER indicators (e. g. appendix 2, lines 496 - 502). Due to the possibility of further processing, different versions of OER are created over time, to which different people have contributed to varying degrees. It is a great challenge to represent these different types of participation through indicators⁵. In order to deal scientifically with versioning of OER, the people involved need to be specified, including their activities. This and similar information

⁵ We see similar problems, for example, with work-in-progress papers or the publication of a paper as a preprint and as a print (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1910 – 1918).

regarding the OER creation process is usually provided, but this information is rather inconsistent, which indicates another characteristic of OER as a scientometric measurement object (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1343 - 1353).

Citation of OER was discussed in the focus groups as problematic for various reasons. An overarching theme was a currently non-existent, self-evident practice in the citation of teaching material. Teaching material should be properly referenced in the same way as scientific publications. However, doubts were expressed as to whether this is always the case in daily practice when creating teaching material (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1812 - 1817). Furthermore, participants noted that the OER citations are technically associated with difficulties (e. g. appendix 2, lines 16 - 24). OER are cited inconsistently. No generally accepted procedure has yet been established in this regard (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1812 - 1817). There are also various recommendations for classic, scientific citations (e.g. the citation style according to APA or Harvard), but they all follow the same pattern. OER citations, on the other hand, follow different structures, depending on whether they are based on classic, scientific citations (author, year, title, place of publication), follow the TULLU rule⁶ (title, author, licence, link, place of origin) or the creative commons recommendation⁷ (title, author, source, licence). It is therefore difficult to automatically process citations of OER.

Use cases

The application of possible OER indicators is discussed in the focus group interviews on three different levels: on the individual level (especially application and appointment procedures), on the institutional level (university or institute evaluations) and in the application as a research method to identify and analyse changes in teaching cultures. In particular, the use of indicators in application and appointment procedures is viewed very critically. Participants point out that quantitative performance evaluations do not reflect high-quality work at the personal level and are thus problematic in their application (e. g. appendix 2, lines 2142 - 2148).

The application of OER indicators at the institutional level is seen far more positively. Individual contributions are very open to this application:

... I actually find this aspect of institutional evaluation and visibility very important. Because if you think about where the digitalisation of teaching and learning is heading from a university strategy perspective, there will certainly be a number of universities that decide not to be visible with their research profile, like Heidelberg University or so, but rather say: we want to develop a strong teaching profile, an international teaching profile, an open teaching profile, an open university, permeability, these are important topics. And you can already present yourself very well by saying as a university: We support our teachers and perhaps also develop an OER policy where support structures are simply offered with the aim of publishing as many high-quality materials as possible on the national OER portal and then also being able to present this in the appropriate place. So I would like to emphasise this use case again as important (appendix 2, lines 149 – 161)

Furthermore, as a third potential application, people discussed that the OER indicators could be used as a research method. In particular, capturing a culture change was mentioned as a possible area of application:

... I think that your OER indicators don't work if you want to somehow measure the individual performance of a person. If you want to measure a cultural change, then maybe an indicator, so to speak, is there a change in a certain discipline, in a certain community? You could use it for that (appendix 2, lines 2227 - 2231)

⁶ <https://open-educational-resources.de/oer-tullu-regel/>

⁷ <https://creativecommons.org/use-remix/>

In this case, the OER indicators function less as a means of making university teaching visible and more as a monitoring tool for the adoption of open practices in higher education.

Consideration of disciplinary differences

In addition to the object of measurement itself and the different use cases, the differences between the subject disciplines played a major role in the focus groups. They noted that different subjects relate to different types of teaching material and that these differences in performance evaluations should not be to the disadvantage of individual subjects (e. g. appendix 2, lines 49 - 54, 300 - 313). The solution to this problem was also discussed by the focus group: field normalisation prevents disadvantages of individual subjects compared to others and provides the basis for subject-specific OER indicator applications and the corresponding fair comparison between disciplines (e. g. appendix 2, line 189 - 191).

Effects of the OER indicators

Desirable effects

In summary, the desirable effects and impacts of OER indicators are the equal treatment of higher education teaching and research within the recognition and reward system (e. g. appendix 2, lines 231 - 237). It is about enabling academics to gain reputation and attention for the time and effort they invest in designing teaching materials (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1311 - 1317). This means that one effect of the OER indicators could be the increased visibility and appreciation of teaching activities and thus a reputational gain for teachers. However, this position was not uncontroversial. At the institutional level, possible positive effects of OER indicators were highlighted in the context of the formation of teaching profiles (analogous to research profiles) of higher education institutions (e. g. appendix 2, lines 751 - 763). As a side effect, the potential effect that the OER indicators act as an incentive structure for the design of OER in higher education teaching was discussed. Openness in teaching would be encouraged and potentially duplication of work would be avoided, as more could be built on the work of others. At the same time these desirable effects could turn into negative ones (e. g. appendix 2, line 568 - 573).

Non-intended effects

The most discussed effect is the concern of an intensification of the focus on quantitative aspects in science (e. g. appendix 2, line 2168 - 2170). There are warnings of the "simplified-counting trap" (e. g. appendix 2, line 368), which means that simple indicators will be used. In a sense, the recognition and reward system is not expected to improve from the inclusion of OER indicators, but merely expanded or shifted. Along with this, participants expect that the non-intended effects of classical scientometric indicators will be transferred to the OER indicators (e. g. appendix 2, line 2331 - 2339). An explicit mention here concerns strategic publishing of documents in the "smallest publishable unit" (e. g. appendix 2, line 2152). There is a fear that this trend will be transferred from the research process to the subject of OER.

Furthermore, non-intended effects are also discussed, which only apply to teaching-related practices. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the fear that OER indicators as performance indicators could lead to an efficiency logic that does not make teaching more visible, but rather more cost-effective for universities in the long run. On the one hand, basic lectures might no longer be updated, but the same teaching materials might be used for years (e. g. appendix 2, lines 563 - 573). And on the other hand, the effect was discussed that teachers who used OER would receive credit for completing fewer courses:

... But as soon as you get into these things and measure something like downloads, then all of a sudden downloads are no longer an indicator for the quality of what you have deposited there, but an indicator that less needs to be done elsewhere, so. If less has to be done in one place, you can imagine what happens to the discussion about teaching loads. Then people say: "How? You are using Open Educational Resources to build up your whole course? And now you want me to give you two SWS? Are you out of your mind? I'll give you one." (appendix 2, lines 590 – 597)

This means that there is a fear that teachers using OER will have to teach two courses instead of one in the future.

Another teaching-related, non-intended effect could be the elimination of the need for university teaching if OER design led to students being able to gather their teaching materials independently at home, thus making the work of universities and university lecturers obsolete (e. g. appendix 2, lines 599 - 603):

... should I really hire someone at my university to knock out everything that is there in terms of teaching? Why should students still come to me?" (appendix 2, lines 978 - 980)

In this context, it is seen as particularly problematic that universities are paid according to their number of students and need students to depend on the university lecturers:

... because universities get paid by how many students are enrolled. That is the main source of income. That's what they get paid for. But if I now say that half of my students don't have to be at my university, but can do coursework online, then the university only gets half the money and is broke (appendix 2, lines 1691 – 1695)

Finally, the negative effect that teachers who are not comfortable with the design and use of OER are disadvantaged by OER indicators should be mentioned. This is not desirable, as teaching should be authentic and there should be no compulsion to use OER (e. g. appendix 2, lines 526 - 531).

Preconditions of OER indicators

In the focus group discussions, the potential OER indicators are discussed both on a practical action level and on a structural meta-level. Regarding the latter, the development towards equal visibility of research and teaching is discussed as a cultural change (e. g. appendix 2, line 2274 - 2275). The prerequisites for this change are seen on a social, an infrastructural and a political level.

The social preconditions are discussed in relation to practices in creating and re-using OER. In this respect, a new attitude would have to emerge that supports and promotes the willingness for open practices (e. g. appendix 2, lines 2368 - 2391). This includes the establishment of a reference culture of OER to counteract the concern that material is illegally reprocessed (e. g. appendix 2, line 1263 - 1267), but also the emergence of a recognised error culture. The aim is that drawing attention to errors is seen as part of the scientific process and does not have to be prevented at all cost (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1258 – 1263, 2368 – 2391).

Furthermore, technical obstacles were seen for the application of the OER indicators. Certain infrastructural requirements would therefore be necessary. These include providing OERs with unique identifiers (e.g. DOIs) (e. g. appendix 2, lines 24 – 31) and marking different versions (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1864 - 1872). In addition, references must be identified as such and the number of citations an OER has received must be tracked (e. g. appendix 2, line 16 - 24). Finally, an infrastructure is desirable that records the reuse or further development of the OER and also allows comments or feedback (e. g. appendix 2, lines 2420 - 2424).

There is consensus that political preconditions for OER indicators are necessary and that structural changes towards greater visibility of teaching must be politically steered (e. g. appendix 2, lines 1677 - 1683).

... Visibility is about power and power structures. I can't just say: "Hm, publish more OER, publish open access". It just doesn't work that way. The only thing that helps is pressure, brute force. DFG saying: "Friends, if you want money from us, you have to publish in open access format". That's the only way to break up cultures. To actually break down power structures. And in this respect, if you want to develop OER indicators, develop them for research funding. Because then you have the sledgehammer, so to speak, with which you can smash kneecaps and persuade professional societies to ultimately buckle. Anything else will somehow not work in the long run. And we have experienced it with digital editions, since 2016 the requirement: Hm, you can do everything, but you have to publish electronically first. And if you then justify well that you want to kill trees to produce books, then you might get money for it. But you publish electronically first. And that worked. And everything else, somehow, with good arguments or, yes, trying to convince, doesn't work at that point. Because the culture and the power structures are simply too entrenched (appendix 2, lines 2568 – 2583)

Allegedly, a "central distribution mechanism" would have to incentivise institutions through the means of OER indicators (e. g. appendix 2, line 322 - 324) in order to enable structural change. In particular, higher education institutions that do not focus on research could strengthen their teaching profile and focus on this area of activity through OER policies (e. g. appendix 2, line 753 - 761).

Alternatives to OER indicators

As already mentioned, scientometric factors were generally viewed critically by the participants in the focus groups, albeit to varying degrees. A number of alternatives were listed which, according to the discussants, are better suited or complementary to quantitative indicators to make higher education teaching more visible.

Peer reviews of teaching material were mentioned as an alternative, i.e. teaching material is reviewed by third parties in the same way as publications. However, this option is considered very difficult to implement due to the already high workload in the science sector (e. g. appendix 2, lines 401 – 403).

Procedures were welcomed by which students are given a more significant voice in identifying and publicising efforts in the area of teaching (e. g. appendix 2, line 2002 - 2004). Teaching evaluations are common at universities at the end of the semester and where students evaluate the courses they have attended according to various predefined criteria were mentioned here as an example, but these were judged unsuitable and in part rather attested to the character of popularity contests. A suitability for the actual visualisation of achievements in the area of higher education teaching was seen less for teaching evaluations (e. g. appendix 2, lines 925 - 935).

As a further alternative, open science portfolios were mentioned:

... for example, I have a section in my CV that says OER, and I simply list what I have done without writing any numbers on it, which I find absolutely legitimate. [...] And at the moment when we don't count, I don't have to list every single course, but I can simply say: "Here, I've put this course online, here and here you can find it, here and here you can look at it". That, I think, is also the important thing about making it visible, that you don't just say I'm doing this, but you can also take a look at my work. (appendix 2, lines 2612 - 2623)

These portfolios could present the activities of a person or institution in detail in various scientific fields. In this context, it would be conceivable to add courses and teaching materials to scientists' CVs in analogy to the information about their own scientific project and publication activities (e. g. appendix 2, lines 2288 - 2305).

Conclusion

In the focus groups, the questions of the suitability of OER and an OER indicator for making higher education teaching visible as well as the expected positive and negative effects of an OER indicator were discussed. A clear position shared by all participants on these questions cannot be derived. The results in their complexity can be presented as follows: OER represent a part of teaching, but not teaching practice in its entirety. The openness of OER makes them visible and accessible for outsiders. They are thus fundamentally suited to making teaching visible as part of science, in analogy to research. However, the relationship between OER and teaching in general requires further investigation.

Qualitative procedures for science evaluation are to be given preference due to the inadequacies of quantitative procedures, especially with regard to the lack of statements on the quality of work results. Also scientometric indicators for OER cannot make qualitative statements about the underlying resources, which is why scientometrics in performance evaluation should only be seen as an accompanying instrument, never as a stand-alone assessment criterion. Against the background of the resource-related impossibility of proceeding purely qualitatively in the evaluation of scientific achievements, quantitative methods nevertheless have a *raison d'être*. Particularly in the current situation, where quantitative methods are predominant, a set of indicators for OER could contribute to making OER, and thus also teaching, a topic within the framework of science evaluation. Currently, this is not yet the case.

OER measurement is very complex. In particular, the property of changeability, which can always lead to new versions by editing and mixing OER with other resources, raises questions about the appropriate consideration of contributors and the attribution of reputation. Furthermore, there are currently structural obstacles such as a lack of citation practice for teaching/learning materials in general and an infrastructure that is not fully suitable for scientometrics.

With a view to a potential OER indicator set, the significance and importance of the measurement results achieved need to be classified against the background of the measurement objective of making teaching more visible. With regard to the measurement levels, the institutional level is particularly interesting. Here, an OER indicator set could contribute to the development and presentation of teaching profiles for higher education institutions. Furthermore, a cultural change towards open teaching could be made visible via OER indicators. Measurements at the individual level of teachers are viewed critically due to the negative experiences from the publication sector.

In developing the potential OER indicator set, the ten principles of the Leiden Manifesto (Hicks et al., 2015) should be taken into account. Based on the discussions held in the focus groups, these include in particular the demands for support of qualitative methods through scientometric applications (Principle 1), the consideration of discipline-specific subject cultures (Principle 6) as well as the individual appreciation of achievements made by individuals in addition to scientometrically determined indicators. A transfer of the Leiden Manifesto principles related to the world of scholarly publishing to the world of OER is imperative.

As an alternative to an OER indicator, there are other qualitative options to visualize teaching. At this point, it is necessary to clarify as to how these can find their way into a science evaluation. With regard to a potential OER indicator, it is interesting to see how the two approaches can complement each other in the sense of an informed peer review.

The participants in the focus group discussions clearly rejected simplified scientometric indicators for OER like countings without the consideration of the special characteristics of the measurement object OER. They argued in line with the position paper of the German Research Foundation, which rejects the limited use of bibliometric indicators and promotes a more comprehensive science assessment (DFG, 2022). Despite comprehensive concerns, however, a balanced set of OER indicators, especially at certain levels of measurement (e.g. at the level of institutions), was considered useful by the focus groups. Likewise, a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to make teaching visible and appreciated as a separate performance category of science assessment was viewed positively.

From our point of view, the estimation of different effects and impacts of the OER indicators by the focus group participants are justified and enriching. Some criticism, on the other hand, are directed less against the use of scientometric indicators on the subject of OER, but rather against the misuse of scientometric indicators in general. These dangers are well known to the scientometric community and are considered in the practice of responsible scientometrics. Against this background, further development and exploration of the idea of an OER indicator set appears worthwhile. The aim of the project group is to develop a comprehensive concept for OER indicators that takes into account the OER characteristics.

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Appendix 1: Focus Group Presentation

Guiding questions

- How do you assess the use of OER indicators as a tool for making higher education teaching visible?
- What potential effects and consequences do you see in the use of OER indicators?

Appendix 2: Transcripts of the Focus Groups

The research data can be requested from the authors.

Appendix 3: Codebook

The codebook can be requested from the authors.